

Speciation of ternary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with L-proline and L-valine in 1,2-propanediol-water mixtures

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Abstract : A computer assisted investigation was made pH metrically on the speciation of ternary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in 0.0–60.0% v/v 1,2-propanediol-water mixtures with L-proline (A) as primary ligand and L-valine (B) as secondary ligand at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ and 303.0 K. The stability constants were refined using computer program MINIQUAD75. The ternary species confirmed were MAB, MABH⁺, MABH₂²⁺ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The stability constants increased linearly with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium due to dominance of electrostatic forces of the cosolvent. The species distribution with pH and speculative structures of the species were also presented.

Keywords : Ternary species, L-proline, L-valine, 1,2-propanediol, MINIQUAD75.

Introduction

Ternary complexes can serve as useful models for gaining a better understanding of enzyme-metal-substrate complexes, which play an important role in metalloenzyme-catalysed biochemical processes. Hence researchers have studied interactions between metal ions and various ligands. In the present investigation, the formation equilibria of ternary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} is studied in 1,2-propanediol(PG)-water mixtures with L-proline as primary ligand and L-valine as secondary ligand. Protonation constants¹ of L-proline and L-valine and stability constants of their binary complexes^{2,3} with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in PG-water mixtures were reported earlier. PG provides the similar physiological conditions where the concept of equivalent solution dielectric constant for protein cavities is applicable⁴.

Results and discussion

Chemical speciation :

The models containing different number of species were tested from the primary alkalimetric data. The stoichiometries and stability constants of the complexes formed

were determined by trying various models for the title system. The calculations were restricted to data obtained in a pH range where no precipitation occurred. The model selected was that which gave the best statistical fit to and which was chemically consistent with the titration data, without giving any systematic bias in residuals. The ternary species detected were MAB, MABH⁺ and MABH₂²⁺ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The log β values of the species of the best-fit model are given in Table 1.

Effect of dielectric constant on stability of ternary complexes :

PG is an amphiprotic and coordinating solvent. It is a structure former and it enhances the water structure in PG-water mixtures. The variation of overall stability constant values or change in free energy with cosolvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. Born's classical treatment⁵ holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. The linear trend observed in log β values indicates that electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions.

Table 1. Parameters of the best-fit chemical models of ternary complexes of L-proline and L-valine with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in PG-water mixtures. Temperature = 303 K, Ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹. SD = standard deviation

PG % v/v	log β_{mlh} (SD)			$\Delta \log K_{\text{MAB}}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MABH}}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MABH}_2}$	log X_{MAB}
	MAB	MABH ⁺	MABH ₂ ²⁺				
Co ^{II}							
0.0	9.34(15)	17.30(24)	24.01(11)	-1.87	0.98	1.16	1.49
10.0	9.71(8)	17.53(13)	23.98(9)	0.06	0.84	0.55	1.93
20.0	9.86(14)	17.53(24)	24.34(11)	0.27	0.85	1.11	1.82
30.0	10.42(30)	17.92(51)	24.69(86)	0.69	0.69	-	3.29
40.0	10.48(33)	18.57(25)	25.66(8)	0.22	1.31	1.93	2.75
50.0	11.24(18)	18.87(23)	25.80(7)	0.34	0.83	1.56	3.08
60.0	11.55(26)	19.66(25)	26.75(9)	0.31	1.28	1.84	3.23
Ni ^{II}							
0.0	12.09(15)	19.09(21)	25.43(7)	0.27	1.05	1.34	3.15
10.0	12.23(8)	19.30(10)	25.37(4)	0.18	0.64	0.42	3.25
20.0	12.77(13)	19.82(15)	26.06(7)	0.28	0.72	0.79	3.36
30.0	13.66(43)	20.71(43)	26.73(22)	0.37	0.77	1.13	3.81
40.0	14.23(15)	21.21(15)	27.09(8)	0.55	1.30	1.21	4.74
50.0	15.15(19)	21.87(19)	27.69(13)	0.84	1.30	1.28	5.32
60.0	15.74(29)	22.92(27)	28.91(18)	0.69	1.40	1.46	6.22
Cu ^{II}							
0.0	16.69(13)	21.56(10)	25.36(5)	-1.42	1.31	1.42	2.35
10.0	18.29(20)	21.51(36)	24.48(36)	0.92	0.78	0.48	5.10
20.0	17.68(20)	22.65(12)	26.31(8)	-1.87	1.42	1.89	3.53
30.0	18.32(46)	22.67(38)	26.36(38)	0.48	1.23	-2.07	4.51
40.0	18.72(12)	23.37(7)	26.58(8)	0.31	1.64	1.44	4.33
50.0	19.23(10)	23.58(6)	26.64(7)	0.31	1.55	1.30	4.65
60.0	19.46(12)	23.99(7)	27.11(7)	0.16	1.40	2.27	4.99

$\Delta \log K_{\text{MAB}} = \log \beta_{\text{MAB}} - \log \beta_{\text{MA}} - \log \beta_{\text{MB}}$
 $\Delta \log K_{\text{MABH}} = \log \beta_{\text{MABH}} - \log \beta_{\text{MAH}} - \log \beta_{\text{MB}}$
 $\Delta \log K_{\text{MABH}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{MABH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{MAH}} - \log \beta_{\text{MBH}}$
 $\log X_{\text{MAB}} = 2 \log \beta_{\text{MAB}} - \log \beta_{\text{MA}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{MB}_2}$

Quantification of change in stability of species :

The change in the stability of the ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified⁶⁻⁹ based on the disproportion constant (log X). Another approach⁷⁻¹¹ to quantify the stability of ternary complexes was based on the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) for the reactions MA with B and M_(aq) with A and B.

The log X and $\Delta \log K$ values calculated from binary and ternary complexes are shown in Table 1. The equations for the calculation of $\Delta \log K$ and log X are given as foot note to the table. These values could not be calculated for some of the systems due to the absence of relevant binary species. The log X values range from 1.49

to 6.22, which are higher than those expected on the statistical basis (0.6). These higher values account for the extra stability of the ternary complexes. The $\Delta \log K$ values of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are higher than those expected on statistical grounds (even though few exceptions have been found for Cu^{II}) indicating the higher stability of the ternary complexes formed by the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} compared to their binary systems.

A stable ternary complex shall be responsible for metal transportation in biological systems and the weak binary metal complexes make the essential metals bioavailable. The increased concentrations of complexing agents make the essential metals unavailable due to the formation of

stable metal complexes.

Complex equilibria :

Both L-proline and L-valine have one dissociable carboxyl proton and one amino group which can associate with a proton. The binary complex species of these ligands refined^{2,3} with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were MA⁺, MA₂ and MAH²⁺. The ternary species detected for these metal ions are MAB, MABH⁺ and MABH₂²⁺ which are formed through Equilibria 1–3.

Typical distribution diagrams are given in Fig. 1. MABH₂²⁺, MABH⁺ and MAB species are formed in the pH range 2.0–7.0. MABH₂²⁺ is formed by the interaction of metal ion with AH₂⁺ and BH₂⁺, because the percentage of metal ion, AH₂⁺ and BH₂⁺ are decreasing with increasing percentage of MABH₂²⁺ (eq. 1). MABH⁺ species is formed by the deprotonation of MABH₂²⁺ (eq. 2) and MAB by the deprotonation of MABH⁺ (eq. 3).

Structures of complexes :

Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are coordinated to amino acids

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams of ternary complexes of proline and valine : (A) Co^{II}, (B) Ni^{II} and (C) Cu^{II} in 50% PG-water mixture.

through carboxyl oxygen and amino nitrogen^{12–14}. Depending upon the nature of the ligands and metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge tentative structures of the complexes are proposed as shown in Fig. 2. Since pKa value of carboxyl group is far less (~2.5) than that of amino/imino group (~9.0), carboxyl oxygen is coordinated to the metal below a pH of 6.0 (Fig. 2a).

Fig. 2. Speculative structures of ternary complexes, where S = solvent or water molecule; M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}.

In the case of MAB, both the ligands act as (O, N) donors (Fig. 2b). MABH^+ species is formed below a pH of 8.0 for all the metals. But the pKa values of amino and imino protons of valine and proline are about 9.4 and 10.4, respectively¹. Hence either amino nitrogen or imino nitrogen is coordinated to the metal (Fig. 2c and d).

Experimental

Solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying compositions of PG (0.0–60.0% v/v) with a Systronics MK-VI digital pH meter maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} with sodium chloride at $303.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$. The effect of variations in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode was accounted for in the form of correction factor¹⁵ ($\log F$). Other experimental details are given elsewhere³. The stability constants of ternary complexes were calculated from the pH metric titration data using MINIQUAD75¹⁶.

Conclusions

(i) The species detected are MABH_2^{2+} , MABH^+ and MAB for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , where A is proline and B is valine.

(ii) The values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the ternary species have extra stability compared to the binary species.

(iii) The linear increase in the stabilities of ternary complexes with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium is due to the dominance of electrostatic forces of PG.

(iv) The study also gives an insight into the metal ion availability and metal ion transport in biofluids. The ternary complexes are more amenable for ‘metal ion transport’ because of their extra stability and the binary complexes make the ‘metal ion to be available’ in biological systems due to their decreased stability.

References

1. P. Bhushanavathi, B. Veeraswami, U. Viplavaprasad and G. N. Rao, *E-J. Chem.*, 2012, **9**, 517.
2. P. Bhushanavathi, B. Veeraswami, U. Viplavaprasad and G. N. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in press (2013).
3. P. Bhushanavathi, B. Veeraswami, U. Viplavaprasad and G. N. Rao, *Chem. Spec. Bioavailab.*, 2013, **25**, 57.
4. H. Sigel, R. B. Martin, R. Tribolet, U. K. Haring and R. M. Balakrishnan, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1985, **152**, 187.
5. M. Born, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, **1**, 45.
6. R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1238.
7. R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2229.
8. H. Sigel, R. Caraco and B. Prijs, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 462.
9. H. Sigel, P. R. Huber, R. Greisser and B. Prijs, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 1198.
10. S. Kida, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1956, **29**, 805.
11. R. B. Martin and R. Prados, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1665.
12. Z. Damaj, A. Naveau, L. Dupont, E. Henon, G. Rogez and E. Guillon, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2009, **12**, 17.
13. S. S. Patil, A. Ganesh, Thakur and R. R. Patil, *Acta Pol. Pharm.*, 2009, **66**, 271.
14. Z. Chen, J. Lin, K. Uchiyama and T. Hobo, *Anal. Sci.*, 2000, **16**, 131.
15. B. B. V. Sailaja, T. Kebede, G. N. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 2004, **74**, 399.
16. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.